

IMPACT DAMAGE AND ITS EFFECT ON THE BUCKLING STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

The development of delaminations induced by low velocity impact and their effect on the axial compressive buckling strength of thin laminated circular cylindrical shells was investigated experimentally. Image Enhanced Backlighting and Structurally Embedded Fiber Optic Sensors were employed for damage assessment. Buckling tests were also conducted on shells with implanted delaminations for comparison purposes and as a means for determining the influence of delamination area on the reduction in buckling strength. Results are compared with finite difference solutions of the buckling equations and linear stability analysis using the ABAQUS finite element package.

Keywords: Impact damage, composite cylinders, buckling.

1. INTRODUCTION

During recent years it has increasingly been recognized that a major weakness of light-weight fiber-reinforced laminate construction is its susceptibility to impact damage. In particular, attention has been focused on barely visible low velocity impact damage because of its significant detrimental effect on structural performance. Strength reductions of up to 40% have been observed in static and fatigue tests conducted on laminate coupons subjected to low velocity impact [1, 2]. Damage due to low velocity impact is mainly internal in nature, occurring in the form of a delamination, which reduces the stiffness of the laminate considerably. A major consequence of delamination in panels subjected to compression, particularly when separation has occurred at an interface away from the mid-plane, is the development of delamination buckling [3], i.e., the local buckling of the thinner of the two separated layers. This can result in an unstable propagation of the 'debond', leading to a global reduction in stiffness and premature overall failure.

The effect of impact damage and delaminations in curved panels and cylindrical shells has received attention only recently. Experimental studies have been conducted to assess the degradation caused by impact damage on the hoop strength and burst pressure of complete circular cylinders [4, 5]. Strength reductions of up to 40% were reported in the latter case. In tests performed with implanted Mylar and Teflon® sheets simulating delaminations in curved cylindrical panels under axial loading [6], axial strength reductions of the order of 20 to 35% were observed, although no delamination buckling or debond growth was reported. An analytical investigation on delamination buckling in axially loaded cylindrical shells [7] has yielded results similar to those obtained for plane laminates, predicting the onset of instability at loads as low as 25% of that of

the undamaged specimen. However, the occurrence of local buckling in cylinders with delaminations has yet to be observed experimentally. Interestingly, the only case where ply buckling (separation and failure of the outermost plies) has been identified as the major failure mode in tests conducted on undamaged graphite/epoxy tubes subjected to axial compression [8]. Obviously, the incidence of a similar failure mode in shells which have pre-existing delaminations (caused by impact or other means) is a strong possibility.

This paper presents a study on the effect of delamination damage, in particular that arising from low velocity impact, on the load carrying capacity of thin composite cylindrical shells under axial compression. Experimentally the work involved three different aspects: (i) creation and assessment of delamination due to lateral impact on circular cylinders, (ii) estimation of degradation in buckling strength resulting from the imposed damage, and (iii) evaluating the influence of delamination size on the reduction in load bearing capacity of the shell. The last aspect was studied by conducting tests on cylinders with 'simulated' delaminations of controlled sizes, obtained by implanting thin Teflon® sheets between the plies of the cylinder during the manufacturing stage.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND TEST SPECIMENS

2.1 Test Specimens

The test specimens were manufactured with glass fiber reinforced epoxy (3M SP-1003) unidirectional material, using a belt wrapping machine to facilitate rolling of the prepreg on to an aluminum cylindrical mandrel. The shell was then bagged and cured at 175°C with a vacuum and external pressure of 500 KPa for two hours. The cylindrical specimens had a mean radius of 100 mm, and average thickness of 1.52 mm. The tests reported here utilized 8-ply cylinders.

2.2 Impact Test Facility

A pendulum impactor, designed for low velocity impacts (less than 5 m/s) and capable of delivering impact energies of up to 150 Joules, was used for the impact tests. The input and rebound velocities of the impactor were measured using a reflective type Object Sensor (TRW OPB 125A) mounted at the location of maximum velocity of the pendulum and connected to an Apple Computer whose internal clock (with a frequency 1.0 MHz) was used for the time measurement.

2.3 Cylinder Models with Implanted Delaminations

Internal delamination damage was simulated by embedding thin sheets of Teflon® (thickness less than 0.025 mm) between the second and third innermost plies of the cylinders. This interface was chosen to conform with the location of the delaminations created in the impact tests. In two of the shells, diamond-shaped implants were placed at the mid-section. These were approximately the same size in area as the real delaminations produced by impact. In all the remaining specimens the inserts covered either the full length or the entire circumference of the shell.

2.4 Delamination Mapping Techniques

Two optical damage assessment techniques were employed to map the delaminations generated in the shells, both prior and subsequent to compression buckling tests.

2.4.1 Damage Detection with Image Enhanced Backlighting

Delaminations were mapped using a simple but highly effective optical damage assessment system, known as the Image Enhanced Backlighting Technique [9]. The technique is specifically suited to mapping of delaminations in translucent materials. It basically involves illuminating the specimen from behind (prior to impact), and capturing the image created by the transmitted light with a CCD camera. The information pertaining to the delamination is extracted from changes caused by its presence in the transmitted intensity. Briefly, the process consists of recording the

images of the specimen taken before and after the impact, subtracting them digitally and then selectively enhancing the grey scale values to provide the desired definition and sharpness in the delamination image. Although the backlighting method does not provide data regarding the depth at which delaminations occur, its sensitivity makes it possible to distinguish between delaminations at different interfaces. The use of this technique permitted multiple impact tests to be performed on a cylinder, by ensuring that each delamination zone was confined to a local area in the shell wall.

2.4.2 Damage Assessment Using Fiber Optic Sensors

In many of the shells, the Structurally Embedded Fiber Optic Damage Assessment System [10] was employed to map the delaminations. The cylinders were bonded into specially designed mounting rings, which facilitated the optical fibers emerging from the cylinder ends to be connected to a coherent light source, while permitting axial loading of the cylinder without stressing the fibers. The optical fibers were embedded between the first and the second innermost plies, perpendicular to the fiber orientation in these plies. They were subjected to an etching treatment developed at UTIAS [10] to tailor their strengths to match the damage threshold level of the composite. The fracture locations of the optical fibers were pin-pointed by the profuse bleeding of light upon interrogation of the fibers using a laser source after the impact event and were marked to obtain a discrete mapping of the delaminated area.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Impact Test Damage

Preliminary tests performed on shells with different thicknesses and ply orientations, employing impactor heads with different radii of curvature, established that the curvature of the projectile head played a critical role in determining the extent of delamination. It was found that there is a limiting value for the radius of curvature of the hemispherical head; when this was exceeded, no delamination was produced, even when energies were high enough to cause severe transverse cracking and fiber failure in the cylinder. The limiting radius was determined to be 25 mm and 51 mm for 6 and 8 ply shells, respectively. Although all impactors with smaller radii induced delaminations, the least amount of transverse cracking on the front and rear surfaces of the shell occurred when the curvature was the least, hence the impactor with the limiting radius of curvature was employed in the majority of the tests.

The particular lay-up employed for the 8 ply shells had only two distinct interfaces between plies of dissimilar orientations, where delaminations could occur: one between the second and the third plies, and the other between the sixth and the seventh plies. The response of the shells being predominantly in the flexural mode, the damage was primarily induced at the innermost interface, while the delamination at the outer interface, when present, was restricted to a very small area. The geometry of the delaminations belonged to two distinct categories, depending upon the magnitude of the impact energy. At energy levels below a threshold value, the induced delamination had the classical "peanut" shape usually observed in impact tests on flat plates [11], whereas at energies above the threshold level, it had an extended "Zee" shape, as seen in Figs. 1a and 1b, respectively. The latter shape, not mentioned hitherto in the literature, was generated repeatedly and consistently in a number of cylinders, and hence identified as a characteristic response specific to cylindrical laminates subjected to impact energies above the threshold level. The straight edges of this delamination, which are typical of this mode, are caused by the presence of transverse cracks in the two innermost plies of the shell wall, which restrain the inter-laminar crack from propagating sideways. It may be noted that the limbs of the "Zee" shape as well as the major axis of the "peanut" delamination, are oriented at 45° to the shell axis, i.e., parallel to the fibers in the lamina immediately below the interface, as predicted by the Bending Stiffness Mismatch [11] and Peel Separation [12] models for delamination. The extended shape in Fig. 1b is clearly due to the action of peel forces described in the latter model; its peculiar asymmetry appears to be caused by the difference in stiffnesses in the axial and circumferential directions of the shell.

Apart from geometry, the major difference between the two modes of damage is in the size of the delamination area. The peanut-shaped ones are much smaller by comparison. In Fig. 2 impact energy is plotted against delamination area for a number of 8-ply shells having a length of about 150 mm. It can be seen that the two modes are separated by a large gap. The peanut-shaped delaminations are all below 1000 sq. mm in size while the Zee shaped ones exceed 2600 sq. mm. The threshold energy is seen to be just under 40 Joules. The direct relationship between impact energy and damage size established earlier for peanut-shaped delaminations [11] appears to hold good, even in the present case, until the threshold level is reached. At this point there is a drastic increase in the delamination growth, indicating a sudden instability in crack propagation. This instability is associated with the change in delamination mode. Above the threshold level the delamination size once again appears to be proportional to the magnitude of energy as indicated by the rising curve in Fig. 2. However, in this region, the shells suffered a considerable amount of extraneous damage in the form of intra-laminar cracks, which also increased in proportion to the energy. This limited the possibility of creating 'clean' delaminations of larger size by increasing the impact energy.

The results plotted in Fig. 2 were obtained from tests performed on different shells. Subsequently, data were also obtained by conducting a series of impacts at different locations on the same shell, which are plotted in Fig. 3. This shell had a length of 145 mm. Again, the sharp transition from one mode to another can be observed at a threshold level of about 38 Joules. The similarity between the lower and upper portions of the curve suggests that the rates of growth of the Peanut and Zee delaminations are about the same, although at higher energies there is additional intra-laminar damage.

The threshold level for transition between the modes was observed to be related to the shell geometry as well as ply configuration. In Fig. 4, the delamination area is plotted against impact energy for shells of three different length-to-radius ratios. At $L/R = 0.6$, the shell was too short to develop the extended delaminations. The threshold level is seen to have risen from about 38 to 48 Joules, between $L/R = 1.5$ and $L/R = 2.7$. The relationship between delamination area and impact energy for shells of the (+45₂, -45₂), lay-up used in the buckling tests are compared with those of shells with (0,0,90,90)_s and (90,90,0,0)_s lay-ups in Fig. 5. The zero-ninety shells are seen to require impacts of much higher energies to develop extended delaminations, while the ninety-zero lay-up requires lower energies. Also the transition from one mode to another is not well defined in these cases. Moreover, the extended delaminations in these two cases were not Zee-shaped, but merely elongated in the axial direction of the shell.

The results obtained with fiber optic sensors in one of the shells (S30) are shown along with the image of the delamination mapped by the backlighting technique in Fig. 6. The two results appear to agree quite well.

3.2 Compression Buckling Tests

The buckling tests were undertaken in a four-screw Tinius Olsen loading machine with a load capacity of 250 KN. The experimental results are presented in graph form in terms of a "knockdown" factor which is the ratio of the buckling load for cylinders with delaminations to those of control shells of the same geometry without any delamination.

It was observed that in shells with the peanut-shaped delaminations, no appreciable reduction in buckling strength occurred. However, the shells with the Zee-shaped delaminations showed 10 to 15% degradation in strength, as can be seen in the plot of knockdown factor versus "percentage delamination area" in Fig. 7.

Buckling tests were also conducted on several shells with simulated delaminations, created by embedding thin sheets of Teflon® between the second and the third inner plies during the manufacturing stage. Two groups of specimens were tested: one having delaminations along the full length of the cylinder, and the other with inserts going around the entire circumference of the shell. The benchmark was established by testing control specimens without any delaminations. The knockdown factors recorded for all shells with implanted Teflon® sheets are plotted in Fig. 8. The abscissa is the ratio of the delamination area to the surface area of the shell. The buckling load

drops steeply in the initial stage, but soon levels off and asymptotes to a value of about 75% of the pristine load. Data belonging to both groups of shells follow the same trend, indicating that the reduction in load is independent of the orientation of the delamination. Also plotted in the figure are the values obtained for two shells which had diamond-shaped Teflon® inserts, providing a closer approximation of the actual delamination created by impact. These had approximately the same area as the Zee-shaped delaminations observed in the impact tests.

In every test with implanted delaminations, the two debonded layers invariably buckled together, developing, in all but one case, the classic asymmetric diamond buckling pattern normally observed in thin cylinders under axial compression. Only the shell with the narrowest axisymmetric Teflon® insert (22 mm wide), buckled into an axisymmetric mode. (The half-wavelength predicted by theory for axisymmetric buckling in this shell is 24 mm.) Even in this case, the layers on either side of the implant appeared to deform together, bulging outward forming an axisymmetric ripple with the same half-wavelength as the width of the delamination. Thus no evidence of delamination buckling was observed in any of these tests, nor was there any indication of propagation of the delamination before the onset of buckling. It appears that the occurrence of delamination buckling in cylindrical shells is restricted by geometry, at least where the thinner layer is on the inside of the shell, as in the present case. The curvature of the cylinder prevents inward axisymmetric deformation of the inner layer, while its buckling into an asymmetric pattern would require radially outward movement which is restricted by the outer layer. In either case, the thinner layer is constrained, and its buckling delayed to match that of the thicker segment. The suppression of delamination buckling in this manner is significant, for it allows the cylinder to carry a much higher load.

These buckling results are also plotted in Fig. 7 over the range of delamination area observed in the impact tests. The shells having impact-induced delaminations are seen to have consistently lower buckling values than those predicted by the curve for the same delamination area. This is probably due to the presence of additional damage caused by the impact, such as the minor delaminations at the upper interface, and the inter-laminar matrix cracks in the two innermost plies. Since the occurrence of such additional damage accompanies any inter-laminar fracture caused by impact damage, it is recommended that the buckling data of shells with simulated delaminations be used with a reduction factor to yield realistic estimates of buckling strength for shells with impact-induced delaminations.

4. ANALYTICAL MODELS

The critical loads were obtained using the ABAQUS eigenvalue buckling solution. A nonlinear static procedure was used to determine the prebuckling reference load. Clamped boundary conditions were used at the ends of the cylinder. The loading on the shell was axial displacement; multi-point constraints were employed to ensure equal displacement of all the nodes at the cylinder end. Typically, for the axisymmetric delaminations, the model consisted of 16 elements along the circumference and 24 across half the length of the cylinder. For the full-length delamination models, the number of elements around the circumference was 48 and the number in the axial direction (over half the shell length) was 8. The elements employed in the model were 9-node quadrilateral, doubly curved, general layered shell elements (ABAQUS S9R5), having 5 degrees-of-freedom per node. The section stiffness data was calculated externally and supplied separately for the delaminated and non-delaminated elements of the shell.

For the non-delaminated elements, classical composite theory was used to calculate the A, B and D matrices, which were input into the analysis. The delaminated regions were modelled by shell elements having an 'equivalent' effective stiffness, whose coefficients were obtained by summation of the corresponding coefficients of the two individual sub-laminates. The summation is based on the assumption of complete separation between the two sub-laminates. This assumption implies that there is no friction or shear transfer from one sub-laminate to the other, and also that their bending and in-plane deformations are totally independent. The resulting membrane stiffness coefficients are identical to those of the non-delaminated element, and the coupling terms (Bij's) smaller, but the most significant effect is the reduction in the magnitude of the bending stiffness terms. For delaminations at mid-thickness and at quarter-thickness, the

resulting bending stiffness terms are respectively 25% and 44% of the corresponding values for the non-delaminated element.

The above simplistic approximation leads to a conservative estimate of the strength of the delaminated cylinder, thus providing a lower bound for the expected reduction in buckling load. In reality, the delaminated region in the shell is bounded by the non-delaminated elements, which restrain the ends of the sub-laminates in the damaged region from independent movement. Even in the case of the whole shell being delaminated, the clamped ends of the cylinder constrain the boundaries of the sub-laminates to stay together. It is also to be noted that since the delaminated regions are modelled by single elements (rather than a separate element for each sub-laminate), the sub-laminates are constrained to buckle together, i.e., 'delamination buckling' by the thinner sub-laminate alone is not considered. Such independent buckling of the thinner sub-laminate was not observed in the tests, which is attributed to the fact that the buckling mode for the cylinder in axial compression involves both inward and outward radial deformations. Hence the unbuckled thicker sub-laminate would suppress the development of buckling deformations in the thinner sub-laminate until the former also reaches its point of instability.

Finite difference solutions for the full length delamination case were also obtained from the linear buckling equations [13], neglecting prebuckling effects associated with the end boundary conditions. In the region of the delamination, the shell elements were regarded as totally separated.

Comparisons of the analytical predictions with test results are given in Fig. 9. Note that the model analyses are only valid for either the full length or axisymmetric delaminations. As expected, it can be seen that the predicted buckling loads are overly conservative. This is attributed to the assumption of complete decoupling between the sub-laminates made in the numerical simulation of the delaminations. In the actual specimens, the contact between the sub-laminates appears to facilitate a finite amount of shear transfer which provides the delaminated regions with a greater flexural rigidity than that estimated. However, the trend to an asymptotic reduced buckling strength, as the ratio of delamination area/shell surface area exceeds about 20%, is observed.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The development of delaminations due to low velocity lateral impact on thin laminated cylindrical shells has been investigated as a function of impact energy, ply orientation and cylinder L/R ratio. The shape of the delamination produced was mapped accurately using two different optical techniques. Two distinct modes of delamination have been identified, and a threshold energy level for changing from one mode to another was determined experimentally for a specific shell geometry. In addition, the effect of inter-ply debonding on the buckling strength of axially loaded cylindrical shells was determined by a series of tests on shells with implanted Teflon® inserts and an empirical load reduction curve obtained. The tests reveal that as the area of delamination approaches about 20% of the total shell area, the buckling strength asymptotes to about 75% of that of the undamaged shell. No delamination buckling was observed in these tests. The results of buckling tests conducted on shells with actual impact damage were also compared with those obtained with simulated delaminations. It was found that the specimens damaged by impact have lower buckling loads, probably due to the presence of additional matrix damage generated by the impact. The analytical models were also found to exhibit similar behaviour, although the asymptotic buckling strength was about 67% of the undamaged value.

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Figure 1: (a) "Peanut" and (b) Extended Delaminations.

Figure 2: Variation of Delamination Area with Impact Energy in Tests Conducted on Fourteen Different Shells.

Figure 3: Variation of Delamination Area with Impact Energy in Tests Conducted on a Single Shell

Figure 4: Effect of Shell Length on Impact Damage

Figure 5: Effect of Ply Orientation on Impact Damage

Figure 6: Delamination Sensing with Structurally Embedded Optical Fibers

Figure 7: Buckling Strength Reduction due to Impact Damage

Figure 8: Knockdown Factors of Shells with Implanted Delaminations

Figure 9: Comparison of Buckling Model Predictions with Test Results